

1 BAIAP2L1 activation following treatment with and resistance to infliximab and adalimumab.

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7 We describe here transcriptional induction of the IAP family protein BAIAP2L1 in patients with
8 autoimmune/inflammatory disease following treatment with a TNF inhibitor. We also observed changes in
9 XIAP expression following treatment with both infliximab and adalimumab consistent with functional
10 relevance of IAP proteins in mediating resistance to clinical intervention in humans with autoimmune and
11 inflammatory diseases through compensatory signaling.
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